

IPERION HS

CALL: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1

GA n. 871034

D.5.6 Prototype studies on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC

Authors: Maurizio Sanesi (CNR), Francesco Coradeschi (CNR), Alessia Spadi (CNR), Federica Spinelli (CNR), Emiliano Degl’Innocenti (CNR)

Document information

Project number	871034	Acronym	IPERION HS
Full title	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science		
Project url	www.iperionhs.eu		
EU Project Officer	Ourania Skondra		

Deliverable	Number	D.5.6	Title	Prototype studies on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC
Work Package	Number	5	Title	Innovative and fully interoperable study of heritage materials

Deliverable nature	☒ prototype ☐ report ☐ demonstrator ☐ other		
Dissemination level	☒ Public ☐ Confidential ☒ Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(30/11/2023)		
Actual delivery date	(30/04/2024)		
Status	Version 1.0	☐ Draft ☒ Final	

Authors (Partner)	Maurizio Sanesi (CNR), Francesco Coradeschi (CNR), Alessia Spadi (CNR), Federica Spinelli (CNR), Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNR)	
Responsible Author	Name Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Partner CNR

Total number of pages	35
Keywords	Data Intergration, FAIR Data

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
22/02/2024	0.1	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	
13/03/2024	0.2	Maurizio Sanesi, Alessia Spadi	
24/04/2024	0.3	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Final revision

DISCLAIMER: This document reflects only the author(s)'s view and the Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abstract

The deliverable "Prototype Studies on Data Structuration and Interfacing with EOSC" (D5.6) builds upon the principles established in D5.2, a key component of Work Package 5 (WP5). WP5 focuses on developing innovative methods and tools for managing and analyzing complex data in digital humanities and heritage science. D5.6 specifically addresses the practical implementation of these principles, aiming to create prototypes that demonstrate their effective use for actual data integration.

Building on the foundation of D5.2, which outlined the principles for integrating heterogeneous data sources, D5.6 developed a prototype for data management strategies based on the concept of overlapping "regions of interest," bridging different disciplines and data production contexts.

The prototypes developed in D5.6 will showcase the practical application of these integration mechanisms, providing a tangible demonstration of how data can be structured, described, and linked across platforms and disciplines. This will contribute to improving data accessibility, interoperability, and reusability within the EOSC, ultimately benefiting researchers, conservators, and other stakeholders in the heritage science domain.

This work aligns with the broader goals of initiatives like ARIADNE, IPERION CH, PARTHENOS, SSHOC, and ARIADNE+, and adheres to relevant international standards and practices promoted by organizations like EOSC, RDA, and DARIAH ERIC.

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

Deliverable D5.6 outlines the development and implementation of innovative prototypes for data management in the field of heritage science. These prototypes build upon the data structuring principles defined in D5.2 and demonstrate their practical application in enhancing the accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of cultural data. Consequently, the prototypes facilitate more effective research and analysis of cultural heritage, enabling researchers to extract valuable insights and deepen our understanding of the past.

The prototypes presented in D5.6 cover a wide range of research scenarios in the field of heritage science, demonstrating the versatility and applicability of the data structuring principles defined in D5.2. These prototypes serve as tangible examples of how these principles can be utilized to address real-world challenges in cultural data management and analysis.

The implementation of these prototypes significantly contributes to the overall project objectives by promoting the sharing and reusability of humanities and cultural heritage data, facilitating collaboration among researchers, and enhancing the effectiveness of research in the field of heritage science.

Ultimately, D5.6 represents a significant step towards realizing a set of tools to build a more robust, accessible, and interoperable cultural data ecosystem that fosters more effective research and a deeper understanding of our cultural and scientific heritage.

The prototype described in D5.6 is based on the principles and technologies described in detail in D5.2, in particular the SSHOCro and the SQARED principles. The next section will provide some highlight of the D5.2 document however, for a detailed overview of the whole context, please see D5.2 Principles on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC.

1.1 From SSHOCro to IPERION ontology

The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, funded by the EU, aimed to develop the social sciences and humanities (SSH) domain within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The SSHOC project developed the SSHOCro ontology, a semantic interoperability framework designed to manage the diverse data encountered in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research. SSHOCro builds upon the existing CIDOC-CRM standard and emphasizes event-centric provenance tracking, enabling researchers to document data collection, analysis methods, and research outcomes at each stage. This facilitates data lifecycle management within SSH disciplines and promotes data sharing and integration across projects.

SSHOCro adopts a bottom-up approach informed by real-world research data and workflows. The core structure centers around the concept of an activity, with properties linking classes to capture the flow of research processes. SSHOCro focuses on practical utility, allowing researchers to create interoperable data pools for reuse. It prioritizes well-understood concepts and has been validated through case studies and community feedback.

The SSHOCro ontology played a significant role in the Humanities and Heritage community data pilot for developing the RAISE platform. SSHOCro's foundation on CIDOC-CRM provided a common ground for describing and connecting data from various sources. This facilitated data integration and mapping into a unified RDF format. The ontology's well-defined structure also enabled domain experts to assess the accuracy of the data mapping process. Furthermore, SSHOCro fostered better communication and collaboration among stakeholders by establishing a shared vocabulary and framework for understanding the data and its relationships.

1.2 SQARED Principles

The SQARED acronym stands for the five core principles of data structuring defined in Deliverable 5.2. Adopting these principles will ensure the consistency, reliability, and accessibility of data, facilitating its integration, analysis, and reuse for various purposes and will ensure the creation of a reliable, accessible, and reusable data ecosystem:

1.2.1 Standardization

Standardization is crucial for ensuring consistency within and across different datasets. This means adopting common and recognized data structures and models, such as industry standards or open file formats. Using shared standards facilitates the integration of data from diverse sources and simplifies analysis and visualization.

1.2.2 Quality

High-quality data is essential for obtaining reliable results. Data quality should be assessed and improved through data validation, verification, and cleaning processes. This includes identifying and correcting errors, handling missing values, and verifying the internal consistency of the data.

1.2.3 Accessibility

Accessible data is crucial for scientific progress. It allows researchers to find and use information easily, fostering collaboration and accelerating discovery. Open data sharing acts as a common language for researchers, ultimately leading to a deeper understanding of the context.

1.2.4 Reuse

Data should be structured to facilitate its reuse for various research, analysis, and preservation purposes. Utilizing open data formats and permissive licenses allows other users to freely access, use, modify, and share the data, with proper attribution. This promotes collaboration and innovation within the research community.

1.2.5 Evolution

Data is constantly evolving and needs to be updated and maintained over time. Mechanisms for managing data changes and updates should be implemented, while ensuring the consistency and accuracy of the information. This includes documenting changes made to the data and creating processes for migrating to new data versions.

1.2.6 Documentation

Clear documentation is essential for transparency and reproducibility of research. Documentation should describe in detail the data collection, transformation, and integration methodologies, as well

as the data structures and formats used. Comprehensive documentation facilitates the understanding and reuse of data by other users.

2. Data management

2.1 Data Workflow

The data integration platform adheres to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) to ensure the effective management and administration of scientific data encoded in different standards and produced through diverse workflows.

The project partners provide datasets containing resources they store and the associated information. The aim of the project is, again, to achieve the integration of these data so that semantics (explicit and implicit) and intrinsic meanings can be extracted.

The problem is complex, as data produced by different institutes refer to scientific-disciplinary fields that are often far apart, which is reflected in the use of standards and cataloguing systems that differ in structure and purpose and are very often not automatically aligned. It was therefore necessary to set up a workflow that not only allows the semanticisation of data within a single reference domain, but also proposes a shared data processing model - valid for several metadata schemes and standards.

The technical phase is therefore supported by a session of analysis and in-depth study of the materials to be processed, carried out with the support of domain experts. This phase guides the use and implementation of tools necessary to achieve the set goal. A summary of the workflow employed is shown in Table 1 below.

Fig. 1 Workflow schema

2.1.1 Data Ingestion

Partners' datasets are uploaded to a CKAN instance for storage and access. First, the original data provided by the partners are uploaded to a data store for storage and access: the project has an instance of the CKAN tool on which files are stored and described. CKAN allows the description of the datasets through a metadata system (essentially, it is a description of the data collection) of the datasets, to which the original files sent by the partners have been associated.

2.1.2 Data Transformation

The project workflow involves converting the original data into an intermediate internal CSV format and then into semantic triples. The original data is converted from various formats (e.g. XML) to a common CSV format for further processing. Then, the data is converted into a semantic triple: a logical-conceptual construct consisting of three properties (entities), namely a subject, an object and a predicate (Subject, Object, Predicate).

The transformation process ensures consistent data organization and facilitates its representation within the knowledge graph framework. In this context data transformation acts as a cornerstone in the process of integrating information from diverse sources into a knowledge graph for cultural heritage research. The transformation of data from the original raw format to a standard format (in this case csv) helps to bridge the gap between the raw, often messy data provided by collaborators and the clean, standardized information required for effective analysis within a knowledge graph framework.

In fact, the initial stage involves parsing the raw data provided by partners. A custom program processes this data, transforming it into corresponding CSV (Comma-Separated Values) files. This ensures a 1:1 relationship between the original files and their corresponding CSV representations. The parsing process essentially restructures the data in a manner that aligns with the tabular format typically used for presenting aggregated data. On these standardized tables it is possible to implement a series of actions about:

- **Data Cleaning:** raw data from various sources often suffers from inconsistencies, errors, and missing values. Data transformation aids in data cleaning by enabling the identification and rectification of these issues. During the parsing stage, for instance, the process ensures consistent data organization, potentially uncovering structural inconsistencies or errors within the original files. Additionally, the transformation process allows for the identification of missing values or outliers. By collaborating with domain experts, researchers can leverage data transformation to implement strategies for handling missing data or removing outliers that might skew analysis.
- **Data Assessment:** data transformation facilitates a deeper assessment of the information content. During the following triplification stage, the process necessitates a detailed analysis of the data to understand its meaning and intended use within the knowledge graph. This analysis allows researchers to assess the quality and relevance of the information for the specific research question at hand. Irrelevant information can be identified and excluded during the selection of relevant information step, ensuring that only the most pertinent data is integrated into the knowledge graph.

- **Information Alignment:** cultural heritage data often originates from diverse sources with varying formats, structures, and vocabularies. During the data transformation process it is possible to align this information to ensure consistent representation within the knowledge graph.

Following the initial parsing, the information contained within the CSV tables undergoes further transformation. A custom Python parser facilitates the conversion of this data into triples using the Turtle (TTL) format.

Through this process, the data is transformed from its original format into a structured and standardized representation, facilitating effective integration and analysis within the knowledge graph framework. This approach allows researchers to leverage the knowledge graph to gain valuable insights from information extracted from various sources, ultimately enhancing research efforts in the field of cultural heritage.

2.1.3 Mapping and Modeling Requirements

The IPERION ontology, designed to facilitate the representation and management of data within the IPERION project, takes after the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) Reference Ontology (SSHOCro). SSHOCro is an extension of the ISO standard CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) and provides a robust and extensible semantic framework for organizing and describing research data across the entire research lifecycle.

Leveraging SSHOCro as the foundation for the IPERION Ontology offers several advantages. Firstly, it aligns IPERION data representation with established standards and best practices within the SSHOC community. Secondly, it facilitates the integration of IPERION data with other SSHOC-based data repositories, enabling data sharing and collaboration. Moreover, the event-centric nature of SSHOCro aligns well with the IPERION project's focus on capturing the temporal and contextual aspects of scientific and cultural heritage data.

To proceed with mapping and modeling, it was necessary to:

1. Conduct an in-depth study of the standards for encoding data and information related to producing entities.
2. Identify a reference ontology on whose semantic basis to construct the triples.

To describe the different types of resources, the standards and regulations associated with them, and to proceed with their mapping and modeling, it was also necessary to analyze the different ontologies already available in the cultural sector. CIDOC-CRM (ISO 21127:2006) was identified as the reference model, also considering its international diffusion in the museum and cultural heritage community. Therefore, the modeling phase consisted of aligning the entities described in the analyzed standards with the properties and classes defined in the CIDOC-CRM ontology. The choice of elements of the CIDOC-CRM conceptual model (i.e., entities and properties) was validated with the contribution of domain experts (archivists, museum conservators, philologists); it was found that the use of CIDOC-CRM facilitates the FAIRification process of the data made available by the project partners, favoring the overcoming of the intrinsic logics of individual disciplines and classification systems.

Through the use of the common ontology, the data were integrated and aligned on the CIDOC-CRM entities and properties. Of particular interest are the entities that were identified as possible alignment points between the different datasets at the time of mapping, as they are present in all these resources:

- Person names → anthroponyms
- Place names → toponyms
- Temporal extremes → dates/periods

To achieve effective data integration, different instances of entities common to multiple datasets must refer to a unique identifier (i.e., a unique and possibly persistent URI), which constitutes the point of contact between competing

descriptions: different information related to the same objects (i.e., people, places, etc.) from different information contexts (archives, museums, libraries, etc.).

By aligning information from diverse sources using a common ontology, researchers can create a unified representation of knowledge that facilitates effective analysis and interpretation. The use of CIDOC-CRM, a widely adopted ontology in the cultural heritage domain, ensures interoperability and promotes FAIR data principles, making the integrated knowledge graph a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners alike.

For more details about mapping and modelling implementation please see IPERION D5.2

2.1.4 Data Import and Graph population

This passage outlines the initial stages of data ingestion within a knowledge management system. The process begins with "RDF Triple Import," where data is imported in a specific format, known as RDF triples, into a storage unit called a "Virtuoso triple store." A custom script, likely a program written in-house, facilitates this import. Following this initial import, the system undergoes "Ontology Population," where the data is categorized and enriched using pre-defined structures called "ontologies." These ontologies ensure consistency and allow the system to understand the relationships between the imported data points. The data for populating the ontology is specifically drawn from two domains: SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) and Heritage Science.

Fig. 2 Ontology browsing example through LodLive

2.1.5 Data Documentation

For each process from acquisition to transformation and fruition of data a descriptive document was created and saved in a repository oncloud.

To ensure transparency and facilitate understanding of the data lifecycle, a comprehensive set of descriptive documents have been meticulously created for each stage of the data journey. These documents span the entire process, from the initial acquisition of raw data all the way through its

transformation and ultimate utilization. This documentation is meticulously organized and stored within an easily accessible, cloud-based repository. This approach allows for efficient retrieval and ensures that anyone working with the data can readily understand its origin, any transformations it has undergone, and ultimately, its intended use.

2.2 Data Tool Suite

2.2.1 The RAISE Tool Suite: Empowering Researchers with Data Integration Capabilities

The RAISE (**R**estore **d**Ata **I**ntegration **S**uit**E**) tool suite, developed by the RESTORE team within the IPERION-HS project (cfr. D5.6), empowers researchers to effectively manage and integrate heterogeneous CH data. RAISE provides a comprehensive set of functionalities for:

- **Data Ingestion:** Seamlessly importing data from various sources and formats;
- **Data Cleaning:** Identifying and correcting errors, inconsistencies, and missing values;
- **Data Verification:** Validating data against established standards and ontologies;
- **Data Semantization:** Enriching data with semantic meaning using standardized vocabularies and ontologies, such as CIDOC-CRM.
- **Linked Open Data (LOD) Creation:** Generating interoperable LOD representations of CH data, enabling advanced exploration and analysis.

By adopting the RAISE toolbox, researchers can transform their data into a valuable asset for research, collaboration, and knowledge discovery, contributing to a more interconnected and accessible CH knowledge base. The tool suite's potential extends beyond the immediate scope of CH research, as its principles and functionalities can be applied to data integration challenges in other domains as well. The available tools have been developed following a modular approach and are aimed at fostering further extensions and development to be easily reused in other projects.

2.2.2 Platform Architecture and Data Standards

The platform employs a modular architecture, allowing the development team to create custom components or integrate existing solutions. The platform could be customised to support different domain-specific standards within the HS and SSH domains, including:

- TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) for texts
- EDM (Europeana Data Model) and MAG (Administrative and Management Metadata), along with MODS and METS (Metadata Object Description Schema), for library-produced content
- EAD (Encoded Archival Description) and EAC (Encoded Archival Context) for archives
- ICCD (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione) standards for cataloging objects in museum collections
- Additional formats and standards used in various heritage science disciplines, such as EDF (European Data Format) and HDF5 (Hierarchical Data Format)

2.2.3 Data Integration Process

The project seeks to establish a new data management and integration model that comprehensively and interconnectedly represents the essential information regarding the tangible and intangible aspects of artifacts studied in the humanities and heritage science disciplines.

The initial project phase involved analyzing partner-provided resources and considering their integration requirements to create a knowledge base aligned with research and production contexts (e.g., libraries, archives, museums). Specific tools were developed for syntactic and semantic mapping of metadata schemes and cataloging systems relevant to each domain of reference, enabling consistent alignment and transformation of datasets.

Subsequently, the project undertook the process of converting partner-provided resources to the project's reference ontology: the international CIDOC-CRM (Conceptual Reference Model). A workflow was developed encompassing various stages, from data collection and storage in the CKAN (Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network) datastore to actual mapping, ontology loading into the Virtuoso triplestore, and population with information from SSH and Heritage Science contexts.

2.2.4 Project Beneficiaries

The primary beneficiaries (i.e. target users) of the project are professionals and researchers specialized in the identified scientific domains, as well as active citizens involved in science-related activities (i.e., citizen scientists). The project aims to provide these users with access to data through various intuitive and user-friendly search interfaces.

3. Prototype

3.1 Prototype definition and functionality

This prototype is a functional model designed to equip researchers with improved data management and analysis tools. In the context of this deliverable (D5.6), a prototype is a functional model created to demonstrate the practical application of data structuring principles established earlier (D5.2). These prototypes aim to enhance researchers' capabilities in managing and analysing complex cultural heritage data. They achieve this by incorporating functionalities like structured data management for efficient organization and retrieval, seamless data transformation for unifying various formats, and enriched data description for improved comprehension. Additionally, the prototypes allow for powerful data linking to uncover hidden connections and advanced data visualization for clear communication of research findings. Essentially, these prototypes serve as tangible examples of how the defined data structuring principles can be utilized in real-world cultural heritage research.

This prototype aims to develop a software platform that enables the integration of datasets from various fields of Digital Humanities and Heritage Science, from data collection to publication. The data integration platform adheres to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) to ensure the effective management and administration of scientific data encoded in different standards and produced through diverse workflows.

As mentioned, the developed prototype will equip researchers with a comprehensive set of functionalities to enhance data management and analysis in the field of cultural heritage:

- **Structured Data Management:** The prototype provides a robust platform for structured data management, enabling researchers to effectively organize, store, and retrieve data. By adhering to standardized data formats and incorporating descriptive metadata, the prototype ensures data consistency, interoperability, and accessibility.
- **Seamless Data Transformation:** The prototype shows linear data transformation, enabling researchers to convert data from diverse formats into a unified and interoperable structure. This capability bridges the gap between disparate data sources, allowing for effortless integration with the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud).
- **Enriched Data Description:** The prototype empowers researchers to enrich data with comprehensive metadata, capturing the context, provenance, and usage guidelines associated with the data. This rich metadata layer enhances data comprehension, enabling users to understand the data's origin, meaning, and intended use.
- **Powerful Data Linking Capabilities:** The prototype provides powerful data linking capabilities, enabling researchers to establish connections between data elements from different sources. This functionality unveils hidden relationships within the data, allowing researchers to identify patterns, trends, and correlations that would otherwise remain hidden.
- **Advanced Data Visualization:** The prototype incorporates advanced data visualization tools, enabling researchers to transform complex data into insightful visualizations. These

visualizations facilitate data exploration, pattern recognition, and the communication of research findings to a wider audience.

Fig. 3 Browsable options for the prototype

3.2 Prototype implementation

The prototype transforms complex information streams into dynamic and interactive visualizations, providing immediate and in-depth insights into:

- **Physical objects**
- **Text**
- **Entities**
- **Places**
- **Manuscript**

The platform offers a comprehensive set of features designed to enhance the user experience and promote effective interaction with data visualization prototypes:

- **Explore Prototypes:** Users can directly interact with the prototypes hosted on the platform, experiencing their capabilities firsthand. This allows users to assess the effectiveness of the visualizations, understand the underlying data structure and manipulation techniques, and evaluate the overall user experience.
- **Utilize Example Data:** To provide a practical learning environment, the platform includes a collection of preloaded example datasets. Users can test the functionalities of the prototypes on these datasets, gaining familiarity with their practical applications and exploring how they can be utilized to visualize and analyze real-world data.
- **Access Documentation:** The platform provides comprehensive documentation, including tutorials and detailed guides, to equip users with the knowledge and skills necessary to fully

utilize the prototypes. This documentation covers the underlying concepts, development process, and step-by-step instructions for effectively interacting with the prototypes.

- **Browsing the graph:** Research can be conducted either on a single data graph or on multiple graphs simultaneously, depending on the needs and complexity of the analysis. A single graph is useful when you want to deeply explore a specific domain or identify relationships between elements within a well-defined context. Multiple connected or interconnected graphs allow you to gain broader overviews, identify cross-cutting patterns, and discover correlations that are not evident in a single graph.

Fig. 4 IPERION-HS prototype Home Page by OVI-CNR

Fig. 5 IPERION-HS prototype Research Page by OVI-CNR

Fig. 6 IPERION-HS prototype Advanced Search Page by OVI-CNR

Illumination prototype

Historiated initial "S" from a Gradual with a Presentation in the Temple

Informations

ILLUMINATION	MANUSCRIPT	MEASUREMENTS
Attributed title:	Historiated Initial "S" from a Gradual with a Presentation in the Temple	
Type:	Illumination	
Described element:	Initial from a Choir Book: Manuscript illumination with the Presentation of Christ in the Temple in an Initial S, from a Gradual	
Author:	Don Silvestro del Gherarducci (1339-1399)	
Production place:	Italy, Florence	
Chronology:	c.1370-c.1375	
Description of the iconographic/decorative apparatus:	The initial S introduced the Mass for the feast of the Purification of the Virgin (2 February) in Corale 2, a Gradual made for the monastery of Santa Maria degli Angeli in Florence in 1370-1375. As in many medieval and Renaissance images, the Purification of the Virgin, indicated by the white dove in Joseph's hands, is conflated with the Circumcision of Christ. Mary and Joseph have entrusted the infant Christ to Simon and Anna, while the priest behind, knife in hand, is ready to perform the circumcision. Painted by Don Silvestro del Gherarducci, the image reveals his debt to Sienese painting. The model for the composition is Ambrogio Lorenzetti's eponymous altarpiece completed in 1342 for the Crescentius Chapel in Siena Cathedral (now in the Uffizi, Florence). The tiled floor imparts a sense of depth to the pictorial space. The intricate designs on the haloes, each displaying a different pattern, emulate the innovative punchwork of Sienese artists from the early 1300s. Three different blue pigments were used in this image: most blue areas were painted with ultramarine, occasionally shaded with an organic red dye which yields a purplish hue, visible in the temple's walls and in the folds of Anna's mantle. Ultramarine was also used for the blue leaves in the border, but azurite was added in the dark blue areas, and the leaves were outlined with indigo.	
Material and technique:	Parchment, mounted on cardboard	
Dimensions:	300 x 270 mm	
Holding institution:	Fitzwilliam Museum, University of Cambridge	
Alternative ID:	Marlay cutting II, 13A	

Photographic documentation

NATURAL LIGHT ELEMENTS

Fig. 7 "Manuscript" demo

3.3 Prototype description

In this section, the prototypes developed for various resource categories are illustrated, each showcasing the project's commitment to interoperable data exploration. These categories encompass:

- **Cultural Heritage Object:** the document prototype transcends a simple digitized image. By embedding metadata and annotations, it unlocks a new dimension of exploration. Users can search for specific terms within a document, explore its provenance through shelfmarks and other identifiers. This empowers researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the document's context and potential connections to other resources.
- **People:** Moving beyond basic biographical details, the "People" prototype explores a dynamic network between people and people and objects. For example authors are linked to the artworks they created, the places they resided in, and the documents they authored.
- **Places:** locations are identified on maps and linked to artworks, historical documents, and even biographical information of notable residents to specific locations. This prototype enables users to explore the heritage of a particular city, region, or historical period.
- **Artworks:** this category serves as a foundation for the Manuscript demo, discussed in the last section of this paragraph. The demo exemplifies the power of interoperability by seamlessly integrating artistic details, historical context, and scientific analysis of a specific artwork.

The prototypes illustrate the added value of the employed approach. It's not just about individual cultural heritage objects or documents, it's about weaving them all together into a rich tapestry of interconnected cultural heritage data to be exploited by researchers.

3.3.1 Cultural Heritage Object

The Cultural Heritage Object prototype is a gateway to explore historical documents, manuscripts and other cultural heritage finds in a multifaceted way. It presents an informative section populated with general metadata harvested from various sources. This section goes beyond basic information about the text itself, offering insights into the people who authored or were mentioned within the document, as well as the locations associated with its creation or content. Whenever possible, these entities are linked through the semantic framework, fostering a network of interconnected information. This approach empowers researchers to delve deeper into the context and significance of cultural heritage objects, enriching their understanding of the past.

"Baliatico XX dal anno 1786 al 1803"

INFORMAZIONI SULL'OGGETTO FISICO

Segnatura:	Fondo Ospedale della Misericordia e Dolce, 5304
Istituto di conservazione:	Archivio di Stato di Prato
Date:	1786-1803
Dimensioni:	390 x 275 x 110 (mm)
Consistenza carte:	1-431
Supporto:	cartaceo
Note:	Legatura originale; in pergamena rivestita in tela

CONTENUTI INFORMATIVI

Descrizione:	"Baliatico XX dal anno 1786 al 1803"
Entità citate nel testo:	Baliatico delli spedali della Misericordia e Dolce di Prato segnato di lettera XX cominciato il dì primo di gennaio 1786 al tempo del signore Jacopo Zeti commissario e tenuto da me Vincenzo Apolloni scrivano di detti spedali.

RISORSE COLLEGATE

["Baliatico XX dal anno 1786 al 1803"](#)

Persone citate nel documento		2429 risultati
Giovan Battista Pini di Filettole Ruoli documentati: Tenutario di Lorenzo Maria		PERSONA CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Giuseppe Del Fu Antonio Paoli Ruoli documentati: Adottante di Cecilia		PERSONA CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Vittoria Ruoli documentati: battezzato, gettanello		PERSONA CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Giovacchino di Luigi e Maria Assunta Grazzini di Prato Ruoli documentati: gettanello		PERSONA CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO

Luoghi citati		98 risultati
Usella		LUOGO CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Vaiano		LUOGO CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Vernio		LUOGO CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO
Colonica		LUOGO CITAZIONE HYPERLINK LEO

Fig. 8 Cultural Heritage Object Prototype

3.3.2 People

The "Person" prototype base is a biographical record, however it also features a dynamic network for exploring an individual's life and influence. This view is meticulously structured with dedicated sections for: general information, collaborations with other people, places connected to the person, a network visualization, and documents and objects linked to the individual. By integrating these elements, the "Person" prototype empowers researchers to delve beyond basic biographical details. It facilitates exploration of the person's collaborative works and associations, the locations that shaped their life and career, their position within a broader web of relationships, and all related resources such as authored documents or associated objects. This comprehensive approach fosters a richer understanding of an individual's contributions and historical context within the cultural heritage domain.

Margherita di Domenico Bandini

Forma documentata:	Margherita di Domenico Bandini, Monna, Donna di Francesco di Marco Datini
Nome proprio:	Margherita
Nome di famiglia:	Bandini
Patronimico:	Domenico Bandini
Genere:	F
Qualifica:	moglie
Moglie di	Francesco di Marco Datini
Altre collaborazioni	<p>MATTEA, MONNA, MARGHERITA, MONNA, E GIOVANNI DI LAPO</p> <p>MARGHERITA, MONNA, E GINEVRA, SUA FIGLIA</p> <p>DATINI FRANCESCO DI MARCO E MARGHERITA, SUA DONNA</p> <p>FRANCESCA E MARGHERITA DI DOMENICO BANDINI</p>

Eventi ↓ Luoghi ↓ Persone ↓ Documenti ↓

EVENTI DOCUMENTATI DELLA VITA DI MARGHERITA DI DOMENICO BANDINI

Nessun evento trovato

LUOGHI COLLEGATI A MARGHERITA DI DOMENICO BANDINI

Luoghi	
Firenze	📍
Pisa	📍
Filetote	📍
Prato	📍
Bologna	📍
Pistola	📍

PERSONE COLLEGATE A MARGHERITA DI DOMENICO BANDINI

Persone	
DATINI FRANCESCO DI MARCO	👤
[Lettere inviate: 1008]	
[Lettere ricevute: 728]	
[Altro: 0]	
[Totale corrispondenza: 1736]	
MAZZEI LAPO, SER	👤
[Lettere inviate: 2]	
[Lettere ricevute: 15]	
[Altro: 0]	
[Totale corrispondenza: 17]	
BANDINI BARTOLOMEO DI DOMENICO	👤
[Lettere inviate: 0]	
[Lettere ricevute: 9]	
[Altro: 0]	
[Totale corrispondenza: 9]	

Fig. 9 Person Prototype

3.3.3 Place

The Place prototype fosters interoperable exploration of cultural heritage data through a multifaceted approach. It utilizes a map interface to geographically locate places of interest. Comprehensive information about each place is provided, including its coordinates and historical names (toponyms). Furthermore, the prototype connects the place to relevant cultural heritage objects and documents, showcasing items produced, found in, or having passed through the location. The prototype also

features notable individuals associated with the place, providing researchers with a comprehensive view of a location's significance within the cultural heritage landscape.

Firenze

The screenshot displays the Firenze Place Prototype interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: 'INFO', 'TOPONIMI ASSOCIATI', and 'RIFERIMENTI'. Below the tabs is a map of Italy with a blue pin on Florence. The interface is divided into four main sections:

- Documenti redatti a Firenze**: Shows 0 results. A sub-section below it also shows 0 results for 'Documenti inviati a Firenze'.
- Documenti con citazione di Firenze**: Shows 1418 results. It lists documents with details such as sender, recipient, and date. For example:
 - TOMMASO DI SER GIOVANNI DA VICO D'ELSA a DATINI FRANCESCO DI MARCO. Segnatura: Fondo Datini, busta 669, inserto 27, codice 110149. Data: 01/05/1395.
 - DATINI FRANCESCO DI MARCO a MARGHERITA DI DOMENICO BANDINI MONNA, DONNA DI FRANCESCO DI MARCO DATINI. Segnatura: Fondo Datini, busta 1089.02, inserto 1423, codice 6300089. Data: 09/05/1394.
 - TOMMASO DI SER GIOVANNI DA VICO D'ELSA a STOLDO DI LORENZO DI SER BERIZO. Segnatura: Fondo Datini, busta 669, inserto 32, codice 511401. Data: 26/08/1394.
 - PUCCI SALVESTRO DI BONGIANNI E BRUNO DI FRANCESCO E COMP a DATINI FRANCESCO DI MARCO. Segnatura: Fondo Datini, busta 1151, inserto 49, codice 131068. Data: 19/09/1394.
- Persone collegate a Firenze**: Shows 1759 results. It lists individuals associated with Florence, such as:
 - ADIMARI BERTO DI MAINARDO. Mittente: 1 occorrenze.
 - ADIMARI DONATO. Mittente: 1 occorrenze.
 - ALTOVITI GUGLIELMO DI BARDO. Destinatario: 1 occorrenze.
 - AMADORI BENEDETTO DI FILIPPO. Mittente: 1 occorrenze.
 - AMMANNATI FRANCESCO DI DONATO DI GUIDO DA PRATO.

Fig. 10 Place Prototype

3.3.4 Artwork

The Artwork prototype offers a comprehensive interface for exploring artworks and their associated documentation. It provides core details about the artwork based on ICCD guidelines. High-resolution, zoomable images are displayed using OpenSeaDragon. The added value resides in the fact that the Artwork prototype integrates historical documentation such as guidebooks, inventories, and museum catalogs, allowing users to navigate between them. Selecting a specific document

dynamically updates both the General Information and Image Viewer sections, enabling users to explore the artwork within its historical context. The Artwork view is further enriched by sections for Historical Records, Analyses, and Art Criticism, alongside a Bibliography listing documented publications associated with the artwork. This interconnected approach fosters a rich exploration experience, allowing users to examine artworks in detail, delve into their historical background, and gain a deeper understanding through comprehensive textual information and references.

Madonna col Bambino e santi

Informazioni

OPERA	SCHEDA STORICA
Autore:	Giovanni da Milano, notizie 1320-1369
Data:	1355-1360
Soggetto:	Madonna col Bambino e santi
Iconclass:	11F61 11H(Barnaba) 11H(Bartolomeo) 11H(Caterina) 11H(Bernardo)
Tipo:	politico
Materia e Tecnica:	tavola pittura a tempera doratura
Misure:	210x245cm
Istituto di conservazione:	Museo di Palazzo Pretorio
Committente:	Francesco Tieri
Stato di conservazione:	buono
Inscrizione:	EGO IOHANINIES DE MEDIOLANO PINXI HOC OPUS
Codice Univoco del Bene (NCT):	090001307
Licenza Immagine:	

Immagine Opera

Notizie Storico-Critiche

Il politico, imponente macchina d'altare, è considerato una delle opere più imponenti del lombardo che qui si firma come Giovanni da Milano: dotato di ben due predelle, costituisce l'unico complesso dell'artista che non abbia subito smembramenti nel corso dei secoli. L'opera fu commissionata dal frate francesco Tieri per lo Spedale della Misericordia di Prato, dove è documentata trovarsi all'altare del «Pellegrino nuovo degli uomini infermi nel 1367. Il complesso, impegnativo per dimensioni e struttura, presenta al centro la Madonna con il Bambino e nei restanti quattro scomparti principali altrettante figure di santi: Santa Caterina d'Alessandria e San Bernardo (sinistra) e i santi patroni dello Spedale, Bartolomeo e Barnaba (destra). Nella prima predella sono descritti episodi salienti delle vite dei santi, mentre la seconda è dedicata al racconto dell'infanzia e alla Passione di Gesù.

Bibliografia

- Bellosi, L./ Angelini, A./ Ragionieri, G., Prato Storia di una città, Firenze, Le Monnier, 1991. A cura di Braudel, F. I-4 pp. 59-61, cat. n. 3
- Bologni G., Prato Storia e Arte, Prato, Azienda Autonoma di Turismo, 1908, pp. 14-15
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 155-156, cat. n. 41
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 22-25
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 26-29
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 30-31
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 32-34
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 35-37
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 40-43
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 44-47
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 48-51
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 52-53
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 54-55
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 56-57, 62-65
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 56-57, 66-71
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 56-57, 72-75
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 56-57, 76-77
- Ciatti, M./ Mannini, M. P., Giovanni da Milano. Il Politico di Prato, Prato, Martini, 2001, pp. 56-61
- De Marchi A., Legati da una Cintola. L'Assunta di Bernardo Daddi e l'identità di una città, Firenze, Mandragora, 2017. A cura di De Marchi, A./ Gnoni Mavarelli, C. pp. 22, 25
- Di Napoli G., Nell'occhio del pittore. La visione svelata dall'arte, Torino, Einaudi, 2016, pp. 7-9
- Mannini, M. P., I Tesori della Città. Pittura del Tre-Quattrocento a Prato. Immagini del Sacro, Prato, 2004. A cura di Cerretelli, C./ Mannini, M. P. II p. 15, cat. n. 3
- Mannini, M. P., Lo Spedale della Misericordia e Dolce di Prato. Storia e Collezioni, Signa, Masso delle Fate Edizioni, 1993. A cura di Carrara Screti, F./ Mannini, M. P. pp. 916-917
- Protesti, A., Il Museo civico di Prato, Firenze, Arti Grafiche Giorgi & Gambi, 1990. A cura di Mannini, M. P. pp. 13-15
- Romagnoli, M., Il Museo di Palazzo Pretorio di Prato, Firenze, Giunti, 2015. A cura di Gnoni Mavarelli, C./ Mannini, M. P. pp. 96-98, cat. n. 9

Fig. 11 Artwork Prototype

3.3.5 Manuscript

The development of a manuscript demo for the IPERION-HS project, focused on the data processing techniques implemented to incorporate information from scientific analyses into the

presentation of artworks. In the following paragraph data provided by Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale (CNR-ISPC) for two artworks is described, followed by the details of the information processing and ingestion into the data lake. The report then outlines the functionalities of the resulting demo, including information sections, visualizations, and linked data exploration.

The data for the manuscript demo originated from the XRAYLab of ISPC-Catania and included information on two artworks:

- Don Silvestro dei Gherarducci (1339-1399), Marlay Cutting It. 13A, Presentation in the Temple, Historiated initial S from a Gradual, 1370-1375 (Cambridge, The Fitzwilliam Museum; Firenze, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana)
- El Greco, Il ritratto di Gentiluomo (oil on panel, 1570), Museo Civico Ursino, Catania

The data consisted of:

- EDF data (and associated text files) containing measurement process results (spectra)
- XRF images (TIFF format) representing pigment distribution on the artwork surface
- Binary spectral data files with readable headers
- An Excel file with metadata about the analyzed objects, including:
 - Description of the cultural heritage object
 - Investigation characteristics and purpose
 - Employed technique (X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy - MAXRF)
 - XRF instrumentation details

The provided information underwent processing as described in the workflow paragraph and the data was ingested into the data lake for mapping and modeling according to the established workflow. This process involved studying the employed techniques and relevant standards to integrate the data into the existing Linked Open Data (LOD) for artworks.

The processing efforts resulted in a functional demo featuring the Marlay Cutting (Presentation in the Temple). The demo offers the following functionalities:

- **Information:** This section provides details about:
 - Illumination: specific information on the analyzed object (illuminated historiated initial S with a Presentation in the Temple scene)
 - Manuscript: general information about the manuscript, including holding institution, shelfmark, description, colophon, historical notes, and bibliography
 - Measurement Campaign: results of the scientific investigation, including employed techniques and parameters
- **Photographic Documentation:** This section utilizes the OpenSeaDragon viewer to display high-resolution, zoomable images of the artwork under different context:
 - Natural Light: view of the artwork under natural light conditions
 - Elements: images resulting from the measurement campaign, categorized based on the analyzed chemical element

- **Details:** This section presents additional information extracted from the artwork's metadata, including anthroponyms and toponyms, which are mapped to existing vocabularies within the LOD. This allows users to explore connections between this artwork and others containing similar entities.

The information sections are designed for user navigation through labels like "Illumination," "Manuscript," and "Measurement." Each label provides textual information, metadata, and relevant images.

The manuscript demo showcases the successful integration of scientific data from X-ray fluorescence analysis into the presentation of artworks. The implemented functionalities allow users to explore various aspects of the artwork, including its artistic details, historical context, and scientific composition. This approach offers a comprehensive and informative user experience for cultural heritage exploration.

By integrating information from different domains, the manuscript demo breaks the silos between the cultural heritage and other scientific domains. Traditionally, these fields have operated in silos, hindering a holistic understanding of artworks. The demo bridges this gap, allowing researchers to exploit information from cultural heritage repositories and scientific databases. This convergence of perspectives fosters a paradigm shift, unveiling new knowledge and insights that were previously hidden.

The core added value lies in the demo's focus on the Marlay Cutting (Presentation in the Temple). This artwork serves as a compelling case study, demonstrating the power of interoperability in action since it offers a multifaceted exploration of the manuscript, encompassing details about the illumination, manuscript Context, scientific measurement.

The functionalities embedded within the demo extend far beyond the exploration of a single artwork. The underlying approach paves the way for a future where cultural heritage and scientific data coexist in a unified environment. This fosters a deeper understanding of our artistic heritage, enabling researchers to:

- Uncover hidden patterns and relationships between artworks and scientific discoveries.
- Develop more precise methods for artwork conservation and restoration.
- Gain a richer understanding of artistic intent and creative processes.

The General Information section, meticulously designed with labels like "Illumination" and "Measurement," exemplifies this interconnectedness. Users can then explore the artwork's artistic details, historical context, and scientific composition. The OpenSeaDragon viewer further enhances this experience, providing high-resolution views of the artwork under natural light and through the lens of scientific analysis.

The demo's success lies in its ability to bridge the gap between seemingly unrelated fields, enabling researchers to draw upon a wealth of information from cultural heritage repositories and scientific databases. This convergence of perspectives fosters a deeper understanding of the world around us, revealing hidden patterns and relationships that would otherwise remain obscure.

The information mapped for the object are reported in Table 1

Fig. 12 Illumination from the Marlay Cutting It. 13A Gradual

Data information	Description	CIDOC class
Title	Main identifying name of the element.	E35 Title
Alternative ID	Any other identifier associated with the element besides the main title.	E42 Identifier
Type	General category to which the element belongs (e.g., painting, manuscript, sculpture).	E55 Type
Shelfmark	Unique identifier used by a specific institution to locate the element.	E42 Identifier
Composition	Breakdown of the element's parts or materials.	:string
Author	Creator(s) of the element.	E21 Person
Datation	Time period associated with the element's creation or origin.	E52 Time-span

Origin	Place of creation or source of the element.	:string
Context/school of reference	Artistic movement, style, or cultural context.	E39 Actor
Description	Detailed account of the element's appearance, content, or features.	:string
Material and technique	Materials used to create the element and the methods employed.	E57 Material
Type of support	Base or carrier on which the element is made (e.g., canvas, paper, wood).	E55 Type
Dimension	Physical measurements of the element (height, width, depth).	E54 Dimension
Information about the text	Description of any textual content on the element (e.g., inscriptions, labels).	:string
Holding institution	Organization currently responsible for caring for the element.	E39 Actor
Specific collocation	Current physical location of the element within the institution.	E53 Place
Other provenance contexts	Past ownership or location history of the element.	E53 Place
Conservation status	Current condition of the element (e.g., good, damaged, under restoration).	E3 Condition State
Images	Digital representations of the element (photographs, scans).	E36 Visual Item

Table 1 Data information, Description, CIDOC class

3.4 Impact and benefits

Implementing data structuring principles and developing prototypes provides several key advantages for cultural heritage research. These advantages include:

3.4.1 Enhanced Data Accessibility:

By adhering to standardized data formats and incorporating comprehensive metadata, data becomes more discoverable and accessible to a wider audience. Researchers, conservators, and

other stakeholders can easily locate and retrieve the data they need, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing across disciplines.

3.4.2 Boosted Interoperability:

Interoperable data seamlessly integrates across diverse platforms and research domains, breaking down silos and enabling researchers to leverage the collective knowledge of the cultural heritage community. This seamless integration facilitates cross-disciplinary research, leading to novel insights and a more holistic understanding of cultural heritage.

3.4.3 Maximized Data Reusability:

Structured and well-documented data becomes an asset, ready to be reused for multiple purposes. Researchers can extract, transform, and analyze the data in new and innovative ways, maximizing its impact and extending its value across the cultural heritage domain.

3.4.4 Streamlined Data Exchange:

The adoption of standardized formats and interoperable data structures streamlines data exchange between institutions and research teams. This seamless data exchange facilitates collaboration, accelerates research progress, and promotes the sharing of valuable cultural heritage knowledge.

3.4.5 Enhanced Data Preservation:

Structured data, coupled with comprehensive metadata, ensures the long-term preservation of cultural heritage information. This structured approach safeguards data integrity, prevents data loss, and ensures that future generations can access and utilize this invaluable heritage.

4. Conclusions

Deliverable D5.6 provides compelling evidence that applying data structuring principles (as described in D.5.2 Principles on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC) is a powerful approach to data management and integration in the field of cultural heritage sciences. By adhering to standardized formats and incorporating descriptive metadata, the project has successfully transformed raw data into a well-organized and accessible resource.

The developed prototypes and the accompanying online infrastructure serve as practical tools for researchers, empowering them to leverage the benefits of structured data. These tools facilitate data discovery, integration, and analysis, enabling researchers to conduct more effective and comprehensive research on cultural heritage.

Table of contents

D.5.6 Prototype studies on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC.....	1
Document information	2
Abstract	4
Narrative (technical) description	5
1. Introduction	5
1.1 From SSHOCro to IPERION ontology	5
1.2 SQARED Principles	6
1.2.1 Standardization	6
1.2.2 Quality	6
1.2.3 Accessibility	6
1.2.4 Reuse	6
1.2.5 Evolution	6
1.2.6 Documentation	6
2. Data management.....	7
2.1 Data Workflow	7
2.1.1 Data Ingestion	8
2.1.2 Data Transformation	8
2.1.3 Mapping and Modeling Requirements	9
2.1.4 Data Import and Graph population	10
2.1.5 Data Documentation	10
2.2 Data Tool Suite.....	11
2.2.1 The RAISE Tool Suite: Empowering Researchers with Data Integration Capabilities.....	11
2.2.2 Platform Architecture and Data Standards	11
2.2.3 Data Integration Process	12
2.2.4 Project Beneficiaries	12
3. Prototype	13
3.1 Prototype definition and functionality.....	13
3.2 Prototype implementation.....	14
3.3 Prototype description.....	17
3.3.1 Cultural Heritage Object.....	18
3.3.2 People	19
3.3.3 Place.....	20
3.3.4 Artwork	21
3.3.5 Manuscript.....	23

3.4 Impact and benefits	27
3.4.1 Enhanced Data Accessibility:	27
3.4.2 Boosted Interoperability:.....	28
3.4.3 Maximized Data Reusability:	28
3.4.4 Streamlined Data Exchange:.....	28
3.4.5 Enhanced Data Preservation:	28
4. Conclusions	28
Table of contents	29
List of figures and tables	30
Abbreviations	31
References.....	32

List of figures and tables

- Fig. 1 Workflow schema, pag. 8
- Fig. 2 Ontology browsing example through LodLive, pag. 11
- Fig. 3 Browsable options for the prototype, pag. 15
- Fig. 4 IPERION-HS prototype Home Page by OVI-CNR, pag. 16
- Fig. 5 IPERION-HS prototype Research Page by OVI-CNR, pag. 17
- Fig. 6 IPERION-HS prototype Advanced Search Page by OVI-CNR, pag. 17
- Fig. 7 "Manuscript" demo, pag. 18
- Fig. 8 Cultural Heritage Object Prototype, pag. 20
- Fig. 9 Person Prototype, pag. 21
- Fig. 10 Place Prototype, pag. 22
- Fig. 11 Artwork Prototype, pag. 24
- Fig. 12 Illumination from the Marlay Cutting It. 13A Gradual, pag. 27

- Table 1 Data information, Description, CIDOC class, pag. 29

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science
HS	Heritage Science
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
DARIAH-IT	Italian national node of Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH-ERIC)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
E-RIHS.it	Italian national node of the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
S&CI	Social and Cultural Innovation
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud Reference Ontology

References

- Bruseker, George, Martin Doerr, e Maria Theodoridou. «PARTHENOS D5.1 Report on the Common Semantic Framework». Zenodo, 30 aprile 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2668433>.
- Bruseker, George, Alessia Bardi, Felix Helfer, Eleni Tsoulouha, Elias Tzortzakakis, e Ksenia Zaytseva. «PARTHENOS D5.7 Report on the Integration of Reference Resources». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2671619>.
- Bekiari, Chrysoula, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «SSHOC D4.18 SSHOC Reference Ontology (beta Version)». Zenodo, 26 marzo 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3744861>.
- Chrysoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS19 Consultation with SSH Data Producers». Zenodo, 30 giugno 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5914407>.
- Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Chrysoula Bekiari, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.19 Mapping of Two Indicative Selected Standards to the Sshocro». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4457496>.
- Baptiste Rouxel, Mathilde Steinsvåg Hansen, Elissa Sibley, Geneviève Michaud, Gianmaria Bottoni, Lorna Ryan, Malaury Lemaître- Salmon, et al. «D4.2 Ready to Use Sample Management System». Zenodo, 24 novembre 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5907939>.
- Chrysoula Bekiari, Athina Kritsotaki, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.20 Sshocro (final Version)». Zenodo, 27 aprile 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6771757>.
- Chrysoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Maurizio Sanesi, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS 20 Selection of SSH Metadata Standards for Mapping to Sshocro». Zenodo, 24 giugno 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4582018>.
- Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, Elisa Brunoni, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot Alpha Release». Zenodo, 31 marzo 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5217113>.